

A NOTE ON THE STRUCTURE OF DISULPHOXIDES

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Constitution of disulphoxides has been a subject of some interest. Mainly structures (I), (II) and (III) appear to have been discussed for these substances :

The structure (I) has been considered unlikely in view of the formation of these substances from sulphonyl halides in which the structure $\text{R}-\text{SO}_2-\text{X}$ is unquestioned. The structure (II) has received some support from measurements of optical rotatory power of certain of these compounds (Hilditch, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1091; Toennies and Eszrine, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 113, 571, 583). But their usual reactions are best explained on the unsymmetrical structure—thiosulphonate (III)—and the work of Smiles *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 176; 1925, 224) would appear to have finally settled the issue in favour of this. These workers have further shown that in compounds, where R and R' are different, isomeric products having both the oxygens attached to one or the other of the sulphur atom are formed, and these isomers are not mutually interconvertible.

Through a series of changes, detailed below, we have now synthesised a few disulphoxides where the symmetrical structure (II) must be assumed. Since these compounds are identical in all respects with the corresponding thiosulphonates (III), already known, it will not be unreasonable to conclude that one of the following isomeric changes (A) or (B), most probably (B), must be taking place during the process of synthesis of these compounds.

The decomposition of a symmetrical structure into unsymmetrical products (as shown by Smiles *et al.*, *loc.cit.*) is not unusual in the chemistry of sulphur-oxygen compounds. For example, the salts of dithionous acid decompose to sulphur and a sulphite, although there is undisputable evidence for a symmetrical structure for this compound (*Curr. Sci.*, 1953, 22, 74).

The sulphonyl chlorides, the starting materials, were prepared by the action of PCl_5 on the alkali sulphonates or by the chlorosulphonation of the appropriate hydrocarbon. These on reduction with zinc and alcohol furnished the corresponding sulphonic acids which by the action of thionyl chloride were converted into the corresponding sulphinyl chlorides, RSOCl . The sulphinyl chlorides in dry petroleum ether reacted with finely divided silver leaf and afforded the appropriate disulphoxides. A summary of the results is presented in Table I.

TABLE I

Disulphoxide prepared.	M.P.		% Sulphur.		Mol. wt.	
	Found.	Authentic.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. $\beta\beta'$ -Dinaphthyl	106-108°	106-108° *	17.80 17.84	18.2	350	385
2. pp' -Ditolyl	76-77°	76° **	22.9 22.7	23.0	272	278
3. 4:4'-Dichlorodiphenyl	136-38°	136-38° †	19.7 19.6	20.0	312	319
4. 4:4'-Dibromodiphenyl	159-60°		15.2†	15.6	484	408

* Otto, Rossing and Troeger, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1893, 47, 97.

** Otto and Gruhn, *Annalen*, 1868, 148, 13.

† Otto, *ibid.*, 1868, 148, 323.

$\beta\beta'$ -Dinaphthyl Disulphoxide.— β -Naphthalenesulphonyl chloride and β -naphthalenesulphinic acid were prepared by the methods of Erdmann (*Annalen*, 1893, 275, 233), Krafft and Roos (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 2261) and Otto and Rossing (*loc. cit.*) respectively. The dry sulphinic acid on treatment with excess of thionyl chloride afforded the β -naphthalenesulphinyl chloride (cf. Hilditch and Smiles, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 4113), m.p. 96-98° (Found: Cl, 16.46, 16.50; S, 15.6. Calc. for $C_{10}H_7(O)ClS$: Cl, 16.84; S, 15.2 per cent).

The well-dried sulphinyl chloride was treated in dry petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) with excess of fine silver leaf for 8 hours at 60°-65°. The residue, left on evaporation of the petroleum ether under reduced pressure, was crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 106-108° (cf. Otto, Rossing and Troeger, *loc. cit.*). Sulphur was estimated and the molecular weight in benzene determined by Beckmann's method (Table I).

pp' -Ditolyl Disulphoxide.—*p*-Toluenesulphonyl chloride and *p*-toluenesulphinic acid were prepared by the method of Bourgeois (*Ber.*, 1885, 18, 436), Krafft and Roos (*loc. cit.* p. 2259), and Graber (*Ber.*, 1876, 9, 1586; *Annalen*, 1867, 142, 95) respectively. The corresponding sulphinyl chloride was prepared by the action of thionyl chloride (Hilditch, *loc. cit.*). The dry sulphinyl chloride in petroleum ether, when treated with excess of fine silver leaf, furnished the pp' -ditolyl disulphoxide (*vide supra*), m.p. 76-77° (Lowenthal and Graber, *Annalen*, 1869, 149, 102). Sulphur and molecular weight in benzene were determined (Table I).

4:4'-Dichloro and 4:4'-Dibromo Disulphoxides.—*p*-Halobenzenesulphonyl chlorides and the corresponding sulphinic acids were prepared (Ullmann *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 642; Gattermann, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 1142; Krafft and Roos, *loc. cit.*). The latter on treatment with thionyl chloride by Hilditch's procedure gave the 4-halobenzenesulphinyl chlorides, which on prolonged treatment with excess of fine silver leaf in dry petroleum ether at 60-65° gave the 4:4'-dihalo disulphoxides (Otto, *loc. cit.*, p. 323). Further work is in progress.

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